
Enhancing Classroom Acoustics

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SUMMARY

Existing Knowledge:

1. Noise levels exceeding WHO recommendations of 35–40 dBA in classrooms disrupt teaching and learning.
2. Reverberation times greater than 0.8 seconds reduce speech clarity, hindering students' understanding.
3. Internal and external noise sources, such as traffic and adjacent classrooms, are prevalent in school environments.

New Insights:

1. Classrooms in SK Bukit Soga, Batu Pahat, recorded background noise above 40 dBA and reverberation times exceeding 1.0 seconds.
2. External traffic noise significantly contributes to acoustic discomfort, with nearby roads impacting classroom noise levels.
3. Teachers experience dissatisfaction, vocal strain, and loss of interest in teaching due to high noise levels.

Putting Research into Practice:

1. **Noise Reduction Strategies:** Install soundproof windows and walls to mitigate external noise from traffic.
2. **Classroom Design Improvements:** Use acoustic panels and absorbent materials to reduce reverberation times.
3. **Teacher Support:** Implement training and voice amplification tools to reduce vocal strain in noisy environments.

Reference:

Tong, Y. G., Md Amin, N. D., Othman, M. H., Abas, N. H., Ewon, U., & Mohd Zaim, M. A. Z. (2022). Assessments of acoustical performance of classrooms and teachers' acoustical comfort in the school environment – A case study. *International Journal of Integrated Engineering*, 14(6), 406–414.
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